

OVER THE HORIZON

INTROSPECTING THE SELF IN FLUX

Conference Proceeding

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Mukherjee's Cultivated Jasmine: A Woman In Exile

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'You may shoot me with your words,
You may cut me with your eyes,
You may kill me with your hatefulness,
But still, like air, I'll rise.'

This is a voice of Maya Angelou, well known American poet, author of seven autobiographies, actress, civil-rights activist, producer and director, off course not alive amongst us but left her words to identify identity of each and every woman on the planet. Indian novels depict Indian life and culture and it resembles the problems generated by individual's life and it is determined by the society. In this way Indian novels reflect typical Indian feminine sensibility and their emotional propensities. These types of themes can be easily identified in works of immigrant writers of Indian English. Bharati Mukherjee's novels deal with the problems of female subjugation and give a new identity to the women of modern times. Self-empowerment is essential for a human being. Here she stresses on women empowerment through the character Jasmine. This paper tries to highlight how Bharati portrays Jasmine as the new age of woman who adopts the new lifestyle in an alien country.

The image of women in fiction has undergone a remarkable change during the last four decades. Women writers have moved away from the traditional portrayals of enduring, self-sacrificing women characters, towards conflicted women searching for identity and no longer characterized their status as victims. Bharati Mukherjee is a prolific Indian born American writer. She presents the contemporary women's struggle and dive deep into the distorted psyche of those immigrants who have been surviving in the conflict of traditional Indian values inherent in their personality.

Jasmine is an odyssey of a powerful woman on her journey to self discovery, which is attained through many experiences of struggle, pain and bitterness in India and America. Her relationships with men at different levels and in different situations play a predominant role in bringing about her self-awareness. It is a tale of endless improvisations risked by a woman. Fortunately, for Jasmine she confronts happy relationship with all the men she loves. Belonging a small village Hasnapur in Punjab state in India, Jyoti becomes Mrs. Jasmine Vijn in Jullundhar then she moves to Florida and is called Jazzy by an American benefactress Lillian Gordon, she reverts to her initial name Jyoti the Punjabi ghetto in Flushing, is renamed Jase or Jassy by her employers in New York, Taylor and Wylie Hayes and their adopted daughter Duff, is transformed into Jane Ripplemeyer as Bud Ripplemeyer's partner in Baden, Iowa, before becoming Jase again to Taylor and Duff Hayes at the end of the novel. These dizzying identity and role changes enable her to explore ever new facets of herself as she adapts to the changes in her life.

In Jasmine the process of life change begins from the entry of Prakash, the first husband of Jasmine. His attitude full of hopes and to touch horizon widens perspective of Jyoti. Unfortunately she loses him just after few months of marriage in a murder trapped for him, but inspired by her late husband, Jasmine does adieu to her old life. Her new self in the widowhood and post-marital loneliness helps her into a mellowed understanding of her future. She found combined efforts of both of them to cherish memories. "We had created life." (1) The process towards a radical change had started the moment she had met Prakash, after which there was no going back for her. After his death too, she courageously breaks the shackles of widowhood. On her way to sea journey to America, her rape-encounter with Half-face, she experiences in herself the strength and fury of Goddess Kali-the sucker of evil men's blood. After this she actually starts living the life of Jasmine. It

is in the bath while cleaning herself she decides to fulfill her mission. Upto this part in the story the Indian identity of Jyoti, who had been named Jasmine by Prakash is almost intact.

Bharati Mukherjee is one among such most sensitive writers of modern India who is undoubtedly a perfect artist capturing the complex subtleties of human relationships in the smooth textures of simple and lyrical idiom. Her writings display the struggle, anguish and rebellion of women in a society of prerogatives and imbalances. In such a literary world that is quickly being packed with many local but foreign authors. Bharati Mukherjee, a scholarly writer who has lived in India, Canada, and the United States, is uniquely positioned to examine the fragmentary nature of characters with "multiple identities", Politics of identity permeate Mukherjee's texts. Her odyssey encompasses five distinct settings, two murders, at least one rape, a maiming, a suicide, and three love affairs. Throughout the course of the novel, the title character's identity, along with her name, changes again and again: from Jyoti to Jasmine, Jasmine to Jazzy, Jazzy to Jase and Jase to Jane. In chronological order, Jasmine moves from Hasnpur, Punjab, to Fowlers Key, Florida (near Tampa), to Flushing, New York, to Manhattan, to Baden, Iowa, and finally is off to California as the novel ends. Her falling in love with Taylor is explained in a very beautiful way: "The love I felt for Taylor that first day had nothing to do with sex. I fell in love with his world, its ease, its careless confidence and graceful self-absorption. I wanted to become the person they thought they saw: humorous, intelligent, refined, affectionate. Not illegal, not murderer, not widowed, raped, destitute, fearful." (2) The confrontation between tradition and modernity is the key factor behind the works of acclaimed migrant writer like Bharati Mukherjee. "Women write differently not because they are different psychologically from men, but because their social experiences are different." – Virginia Woolf. (3)

Jasmine belongs a rural background where she saw existence of woman to be as SATI (A woman jumps into fire after her husband's death). From there to here- a total transformation of life in America reveals her strength. Jasmine undergoes her next transformation from a dutiful traditional Indian wife Jasmine to be an independent entity. Jasmine creates a new world consisting of new ideas and values, constantly unmasking her past to establish a new cultural identity by incorporating new desires, skills, and habits. This seems absolute fruitful to alter her attitude towards relations and life. She looks an impressive adopter and learner. Jasmine learns the different ways to live and adjust in alien culture. Here Lillian Gordon bestows upon her the nickname 'Jazzy', a symbol of her entrance into and acceptance of American culture. Living with an Indian family, she finds it completely motionless and Jasmine takes decision to take her away from staying with them. Actually she desires to discontinue her every relations and memory from Indians who take her into memories of panic past. Her migration to America as a caretaker for an American family sets another benchmark in protagonist's journey. While living with the Hayes, Jasmine begins to master the English language, empowering herself to further appropriate American culture. In the Hayes household, Jasmine becomes aware of her racial identity because Taylor and his friends understood that she was from South Asia and tried to associate her with that community. Jasmine constantly shuttles in search of a concrete identity. But though Jasmine creates a new identity for every new situation, her former identities are never completely erased. They emerge in specific moments in the text and exacerbate the tension, thereby causing Jasmine to create another more dominant identity.

When Jasmine was seven, she was told by a fortune teller that she would become a widow at the age of seventeen and also talked about her journey to an alien land. Jasmine didn't accept with the statement of what he said. She disagrees strongly with him and tells fortune teller a crazy man. When she attains the marriage age, her grandmother selects an old man as a bride groom, but she boldly rejects the proposal. It shows rebellious nature of Jasmine. Her marriage also has taken place in an unconventional method, against the will and wish of her elders. She falls in love with the voice of a Christian guy named Prakash and marries him in the Registrar office. In Indian terms, even according to many cultures Jasmine is not considered a moral character. Bharati Mukherjee herself doesn't consider "Jasmine "a good person," she is a "black-mailer" and a "murderer" who has dumped a good crippled man. But she considers her a "love goddess" a "life-force." She is not moral in the conventional sense but her morality is her own way of looking at life. She is a 'path-finder' and pierces her way through the dense jungle of problems. Every movement adds to her self-confidence and her experience guides her future course of action. She is fluid and adjusting and justifies her each and every role." (4)

Mukherjee suggests that the only way to survive in the new land is to be like Jasmine, not like other fragile women who don't come out from the weaved cocoon of defined life styles and definitions. Jasmine is such an inspiring character who believes in give and take which is universal reality on the planet to survive gently. She learns quickly that in America nothing last similarly in life. The hardest lessons teach the best, make life easiest. Nothing is forever, nothing is so terrible from which no one can recover. "Living in America, she learns to fend for herself till she 'learnt to live not for her husband or for her children but for herself.'" (5) She sheds taboos of Indian widows inspite of her village astrologer's earlier prediction that to be 'Sati', she emerges as 'Kali.'

Human life has many obstacles and odds. Only some of them emerge as survivors whereas some of them surrender to

fate. Here, Jasmine displays courage and the ability to survive in her various identities. She discovers more and more of herself in the journey of multiple identities. She approaches life in a positive tone and leads a successful life. She creates a new world consisting of new ideas and values. Though Jasmine seeks to distance herself from cultural expectations and tradition the possibility of independence and agency exist in reality. Throughout the novel, Jasmine experiences enormous situations which bring out the violence and mental trauma in her. She not only faces physical violence, but also mental violence that forces her to be born as a different person in various phases of her life. The progression of Jasmine from one stage of evolution to the other stage of life is portrayed as a courageous character.

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